

THE ROLE OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN MEDICINE

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ABSTRACT

The recent boost in advancement of technology and the availability of AI platforms gave a huge chance the healthcare to be developed. Obviously, technology itself has played an indispensable role in revolutionizing the way various diseases are treated and in the diagnostics as well. Artificial intelligence, gifted tremendous opportunities and made the treatment process much easier. In this thesis, various aspects and privileges of “computerized healthcare” will be discussed.

Keywords: computerized healthcare, AI, technology, Oxipit Quality, Tempus, GNS Healthcare

Admittedly, it is highly advantageous for humanity that both technology and AI have touched the every aspect of medical sector, ranging from reading and analyzing the genetic material to difficult operations done by robots. One of the bright examples for this, is the “Oxipit Quality” machine, which is an AI-powered tool, invented in Lithuania, to enhance diagnostic accuracy in radiology. It helps to avoid discrepancies and missed findings by analyzing final reports of radiologists and medical images taken with X-rays. The workflow of the machine is here:

1. Analysis. The system reviews the reports of a doctor and medical images.
2. Detection. Identifies any errors or mismatches between the physician’s reports and the images given.
3. Notification. If any error is found in the report, the computer alerts the radiologist about that.

Obviously, this machine is very helpful in identifying any diagnostic errors, and detecting subtle findings, which could be overlooked with human eyes. “Oxipit Quality” is not the only platform that helps physicians avoid potential mistakes in giving patient outcomes, there are also: Aidoc, Qure.ai, Lunit Insight and others that are extremely useful for increasing the accuracy of treatment process.

The other AI-powered platform was made by “Tempus”, mainly to provide a holistic view of each patient’s condition by analyzing the genetic material and collecting clinical data from electronic health records. Recently Tempus started to

predict the future potential disorders according to the genetic material provided. Which can give the people the chance to warn that possible disorder in an organism.

Also, personalized medicine is getting much attention, especially the AI-based platforms that provide therapeutic strategies and uncover the cause-and-effect relationships in complex biological and healthcare data.

Conclusion.

In conclusion, I once again restate my view that, the development of AI and technology is the prime motive behind such a tremendous boost in medical sector, due to the increased accuracy in treatment, anticipating the potential diseases in patients, predicting the reaction of an organism to particular